

22NRM01 TraMeXI

D1 – Recommendations on which reference radiation qualities should be included into IEC 61267 and evidence submitted to IEC SC62C WG 3 and IAEA CRP E24024 officers

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Deliverable Cover Sheet

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Glossary

HVL – in this document HVL is used as a synonym for the 1st Half-value Layer (HVL) in aluminium (Al) in mm.

RRQs – recommended radiation qualities

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1 Introduction

This document gives recommendations on which reference radiation qualities should be included into IEC 61267 (RRQs), for all modalities.

2 Evaluation of the range of relevant radiation qualities

2.1 Survey of clinical radiation qualities

Information on the most common anode material, total filtration, X-ray tube voltage and anode angle combinations used in clinics was obtained from technical specifications provided by X-ray system manufacturers. This information was then combined with the results of a survey intended for medical physicists or other technical personnel responsible for dosimetry measurements of X-ray imaging devices used in hospitals, to identify the combinations typically used in clinical practice. [1].

2.2 Range of radiation quality parameters

Deterministic radiation transport simulation tools were used to simulate the spectra for all combinations of anode material, total filtration, X-ray tube voltage and anode angle found. These spectra were used to access the related radiation quality parameters: HVL, mean energy and SNR_{In}^2 .

2.3 Measurement of clinical spectra

Clinical spectra were measured for mammography, C-arm and conventional X-ray imaging equipment, see Table 1. Measurements on different equipment available at different clinical and other sites allowed to confirm the table of clinical radiation qualities compiled before and were used to validate spectra obtained by the deterministic radiation transport simulation tools.

Modality	Manufacturer	Device Model
Conventional, mobile	Siemens Healthineers	Mobilet Mira Max Portable
Conventional, stationary	Canon/Arcoma	Arcoma Precision T3
Conventional, stationary	Communications & Power Industries	Indico 100
Conventional, stationary	Philips	Horizontal Diagnost
Conventional, stationary	Philips	BuckyDiagnost
Conventional, stationary	Siemens Healthineers	Luminos dRF Max
Conventional, stationary	Siemens Healthineers	Multix Fusion
Conventional, stationary	Siemens Healthineers	Ysio Max
Dental, intraoral	Dentsply Sirona	Heliodent Plus
Mammography	AlphaRT	Alpha RT
Mammography	Planmed	Planmed Clarity
Mammography	Fujifilm	Amulet Innovality
Mammography	GE	Senographe Pristina
Mammography	Siemens Healthineers	Mammomat 3000

Mammography	Siemens Healthineers	Mammomat Revelation
C-arm, mobile	Philips	BV Endura
C-arm, mobile	Siemens Healthineers	Cios Connect
C-arm, mobile	Ziehm Imaging	Ziehm Solo
C-arm, mobile	Ziehm Imaging	Ziehm Vision
C-arm, stationary	Siemens Healthineers	Artis Q
C-arm, stationary	Siemens Healthineers	Artis zee multi-purpose
C-arm, stationary	Siemens Healthineers	Artis icono biplane
Therapy	Womed	T-200

Table 1: Clinical devices investigated in A1.2.2

2.4 Validation by Monte Carlo simulation methods

Monte Carlo simulations were performed for three devices where spectrometry was performed: Planmed Clarity, Indico 100 and Artis Q. The aim was to give an additional validation of the deterministic radiation transport simulation tools.

Very close agreement was found between Monte Carlo simulations and deterministic calculations performed with the software SpekPy software. Small differences were mainly caused by simplifications included in the SpekPy models, e.g. the absence of Re in the W-Re anode. Comparison of simulated and measured spectra showed larger differences for some devices. Based on further tests, it is assumed that the main cause of the difference is anode ageing of the real anode, which affects the shape of the photon fluence spectrum and is not taken into account in the Monte Carlo simulation or SpekPy calculations. The detailed investigation can be found in literature [2].

2.5 Capability checks for calibration laboratories

Laboratory spectra were measured for RQR + Cu radiation qualities at several calibration laboratories. The aim was to assess the ability of laboratories to produce new RRQs. The inter-laboratory agreement (as expressed by the resulting HVL values) was within the typical limits of standardised radiation qualities.

2.6 Clinically relevant radiation conditions

Based on the described methodology clinically relevant radiation conditions were derived (Table 2 to Table 5). For CT, it is known that one manufacturer also uses Ag filtration, but no technical details were shared with the consortium.

Modality	Voltage range [kV]	Al-filtration range ^a [mm]	Cu-filtration range [mm]	HVL range [mm Al]
Diagnostic radiography	50 - 130	2.5 - 4.5	0 - 0.3	1.7 - 9.4
C-arm, mobile	50 - 120	2.7 - 5.8	0 - 0.2	1.4 - 9.3
C-arm, stationary	60 - 150	2.5 - 3.5	0 - 0.9	2.1 - 12.6
Dental, intraoral	50 - 70	1.5	-	1.3 - 1.8
Dental, extraoral, including CBCT	60 - 120	2.5 - 4.5	0 - 0.5	2.2 - 10.2
CT	70 - 150	2.5 - 10	-	2.4 - 9.4

Table 2: Copper and aluminium filtrations

Modality	Voltage range [kV]	Al-filtration range ^a [mm]	Sn-filtration range [mm]	HVL range [mm Al]
CT	100 - 150	6 - 7	0.4 - 0.85	10.3 - 15.2

Table 3: Tin filtrations

Modality	Voltage range [kV]	Al-filtration range ^a [mm]	Au-filtration range [mm]	HVL range [mm Al]
CT	120 - 140	6 - 7.5	0.07	9.3 - 10.3

Table 4: Gold filtrations

Anode Materials	Filter Material	Thickness [μm]	Voltage range [kV]	HVL range [mm Al] ^{b, c}	Comments ^d
Mo	Mo	30	20 - 35	0.1 - 0.6	conv, DBT
Mo Rh (GE ^e)	Rh	25, 30 (Instrumentarium)	20 - 35 -	0.2 - 0.7 -	conv, DBT
Mo, Rh	Cu	250	49	-	CEM (GE ^e)
Rh	Ag	30	20 - 35	0.3 - 0.7	conv (GE ^e), DBT
W	Rh	50, 60 (Planmed)	20 - 40 -	0.3 - 0.9	conv, DBT
W	Ag	50, 75 (Planmed)	20 - 40	0.3 - 1.0	conv, DBT
W	Al	500 - 1000	20 - 50	0.2 - 1.3	conv, DBT, CEM
W	Ti	1000 - 1300	49	3.1 - 3.7	CEM (Siemens)
W	Cu	300	45, 50	2.9 - 3.8	CEM (Hologic)

^aThis includes the inherent filtration as an aluminium equivalent thickness.

^bLower limits have been rounded down and upper limits have been rounded up.

^cThe upper limit of the HVL range has been calculated taking into account a compression paddle, which has been conservatively estimated by increasing the upper HVL value by 0.2 mm Al, the effect of tube aging was not considered for the given ranges and can lead to an additional increase of 12 % in HVL values.

^dconventional (conv), contrast-enhanced mammography (CEM), digital breast tomosynthesis (DBT)

^eGeneral Electric (manufacturer)

Table 5: Mammography

3 Recommendations on which new reference radiation qualities should be included in IEC 61267 (RRQs)

3.1 Mobile and stationary C-arms

3.1.1 Clinically relevant and physical representative radiation qualities (CPRQs) for copper-filtered beams

Based on chapter 2, it is recommended to update RQC radiation qualities for better coverage of the radiation qualities encountered for mobile and stationary C-arms. The new RQC radiation qualities should be selected to be suitable for HVL interpolation. To avoid the influence of characteristic lines, the Al filter must be placed between the copper filter and the detector. The selection presented in Table 6 represents an approach where these requirements are fulfilled by the use of 3 newly defined thicknesses of copper filters.

Realized on basis of	Tube voltage [kV]	Typical total filtration RQR [mm Al]	0.1 mm Cu	0.2 mm Cu	0.25 mm Cu	0.3 mm Cu	0.5 mm Cu	0.9 mm Cu	1.5 mm Cu	2.0 mm Cu
RQR 3	50	2.46	New			New	RQC 3			
RQR 4	60	2.68	New			New		New		
RQR 5	70	2.83	New			New		New	RQC 5	
RQR 8	100	3.36	New	RQT 8		New		New		RQC 8
RQR 9	120	3.73	New		RQT 9	New		New		
RQR 10	150	4.38	New			RQT 10		New		

Table 6: CPRQs for copper-filtered beams. Current IEC reference radiation qualities are given for comparison.

Comparing the HVL values for these tube voltage/filter combinations with the radiation qualities currently defined, it can be seen that the HVL values are in several cases, which is indicated in Table 7 by colours. Therefore, a reduction of the number of radiation conditions seems feasible if it can be ensured that similar HVLs result in similar responses of typical detectors.

Realized on basis of	Tube voltage [kV]	Typical total filtration RQR [mm Al]	0.1 mm Cu	0.2 mm Cu	0.25 mm Cu	0.3 mm Cu	0.5 mm Cu	0.9 mm Cu	1.5 mm Cu	2.0 mm Cu
RQR 3	50	2.46	2.8	-	-	3.9	(4.5)	-	-	-
RQR 4	60	2.68	3.4	-	-	4.7	-	6.5	-	-
RQR 5	70	2.83	4.1	-	-	5.7	-	7.7	(8.4)	-
RQR 8	100	3.36	5.9	(6.9)	-	7.8	-	10.2	-	(11.5)
RQR 9	120	3.73	7.0	-	(8.4)	9.0	-	11.3	-	-
RQR 10	150	4.38	8.4	-	-	10.3	-	12.6	-	-

Table 7: HVLs of CPRQs for copper-filtered beams. Current IEC reference radiation qualities are given for comparison. The HVL values are the mean value of the HVLs values reported by the laboratories that have established the radiation qualities within the scope of the project, except for RQR 4 with 0.1 mm and 0.3 mm Cu, which were derived by SpekPy (by CMI). RQR 3 + 0.9 mm Cu is not a new RRQ.

Figure 1: Tube voltage in dependence of HVLs of CPRQs for copper-filtered beams provided by ENEA. Current IEC reference radiation qualities are given for comparison. There is an overlap for many radiation qualities. A survey was conducted within the scope of this project, including questions on filters typically used in clinical practice [1]. The circle diameters indicate the number of users reporting the use of the respective filters. For the evaluation, several assumptions were required, as the questionnaire only captured the minimum and maximum voltages applied in clinical practice for each filter.

For lower HVL values, it is important to have several thicknesses of Cu filters available, for the same HVL, as this can result in different calibration coefficients (Figure 1 and Figure 2). For high HVL values same HVLs give similar calibration coefficients for a different thickness of the filters (compare 0.3 mm Cu and 0.9 mm Cu in Figure 2 and Figure 3), for typical reference class ionization chamber.

Figure 2: Calibration coefficients of a typical reference class ionization chamber (Exradin A3) for selected radiation qualities (normalized to RQR 5), provided by PTB.

Figure 3: Calibration coefficients of a typical reference class ionization chamber (Exradin A3) for selected radiation qualities (normalized to RQR 5), provided by VSL.

3.1.2 RRQs for copper-filtered beams

With this knowledge the following combinations are proposed for future updates of IEC 61267, effectively removing RQT and RQC in its current form from the standard and introducing a harmonized set of copper-filtered beams, that can be established with only 3 copper filters based on RQR.

Realized on basis of	Tube voltage [kV]	0.1 mm Cu	0.3 mm Cu	0.9 mm Cu
RQR 3	50	2.8	3.9	-
RQR 4	60	3.4	4.7	6.5
RQR 5	70	4.1	5.7	7.7
RQR 8	100	5.9	7.8	10.2
RQR 9	120	7.0	9.0	11.3
RQR 10	150	8.4	10.3	12.6

Table 8: Recommended new reference radiation qualities (RRQs) based on Cu filtration and their HVL values derived as average values reported by the TraMeXI partners, except for RQR 4 with 0.1 mm and 0.3 mm Cu, which were derived by SpekPy (by CMI). RQR 3 + 0.9 mm Cu is not a new RRQ.

These radiation qualities could potentially serve as substitutes for RQA radiation conditions; however, no experiments were conducted within the scope of this project to verify whether identical HVL values produce comparable results in typical tests or calibrations when transitioning from copper to aluminium.

Figure 4: Values of 1st HVL in Al of 40 - 150 kV range measured clinical spectra compared with HVL values of RQR (circles), RQT (squares), RQA (pentagrams), and RQC (hexagrams) reference radiation qualities according to IEC 61267 and with the recommended new reference radiation qualities based on RQR with added 0.1 mm Cu (diamonds), 0.3 mm Cu (right-pointing triangles), and 0.9 mm Cu (upward-pointing triangles), provided by CMI.

3.2 Mammography

The voltage range for mammography is 20 to 50 kV, with voltages above 35 kV only reported for contrast-enhanced mammography.

The results showed that tungsten (W) is the most common anode material for the reported devices (13) followed by molybdenum (Mo) (5). Only two devices with rhodium (Rh) anodes were reported (Senographe Pristina and Essential, GE, USA). It must be noted that a specific filter thickness is linked with a specific anode material. E.g., the typical thickness of Rh filters for Mo anodes is 25 μm , while 50 μm is the most used thickness for W anodes (5 scanners were identified). This filter is also used for tomosynthesis by some manufacturers (Siemens, Planmed).

Another common filter is 50 μm of silver (Ag), this was found for 4 scanner models (Giotto, Hologic, United Imaging). One manufacturer (Planmed) has a deviating thickness for Ag filters (75 μm).

Some manufacturers also use Al filters for tomosynthesis, e.g., 700 μm Al filters for (Hologic, Fuji), there's also one device using 500 μm Al (Metaltronica).

For contrast enhanced mammography also Cu and Ti filters are relevant. These filters are used for the high energy radiation fields between 45 and 49 keV.

Clinical scanners manufactured by United Imaging, Giotto, Siemens, Fuji, Metaltronica, and Hologic offer W anodes in combination with 50 μm Rh filters. Planmed uses 60 μm Rh filters. Therefore, it can be concluded that Rh filters are widely used.

On the other hand, there were no GE scanners using W anodes.

3.2.1 Clinically relevant and physical representative radiation qualities (CPRQs) for mammography

It was concluded that most modern clinical units use W anode with 50 μm Rh filters followed by W anode with 50 μm Ag, followed by W anode with 700 μm Al (for tomosynthesis). Based on this, it can be argued that all these combinations are more relevant for standardization than Mo/Mo. On the other hand, typical mammography reference standard ionization chambers used by SSDs will provide very similar calibration coefficients for W/Al and W/Ag radiation fields for same HVL values, while the HVL values for Mo/Mo are typically lower (c.f., Figure 5). As Mo/Mo is still available at popular mammography devices (e.g., Mammomat 3000) this combination is still relevant. The reference radiation qualities should be defined to cover the full HVL range of conventional mammography, for HVL interpolation with ionization chambers.

Figure 5: Calibration coefficients of a typical reference class ionization chamber (Radcal RC6M) for typical mammography radiation qualities, provided by PTB.

3.2.2 Influence of compression paddles and tube aging

In a clinical situation the compression paddle will act as an additional filter (Figure 6). A calibration lab can mimic this additional filtration, extending the mammography HVL range to higher values. It was calculated by PTB, that for a W50/AI700 spectrum, an additional aluminium filter of 0.16 mm will have the same effect on HVL as a 3 mm PMMA compression paddle, which is considered to result in the highest HVL value for clinical situations. This will result in an HVL value of approximately 0.96 mm Al.

Figure 6: Fluence spectra for W28/Rh50 for laboratory conditions (MC_{lab}) Mammomat Revelation without compression paddle (MC_{clinic}) and Mammomat Revelation with 3 mm PMMA compression paddle ($MC_{clinic, CP}$), provided by PTB.

In addition, by comparing measurements with SpekPy simulations (both without compression paddle), it was found that the HVL at clinical Mo/Mo mammography devices can be 13 % larger in measurement compared to SpekPy, this effect is most likely caused by tube aging (highest deviations were found for an older Mammomat 3000). Similar effects were found for C-arm systems and published within the scope of this project [1]. Based on this knowledge, a calibration lab could use an additional aluminium filter that results in an HVL

value of 1.08 mm Al to consider tube aging and the compression paddle at the same time. To achieve this HVL value for W50/Al700 the additional aluminium filter must be 0.18 mm.

Therefore, an additional aluminium filter of 0.34 mm (0.16 mm for the compression paddle and 0.18 mm for tube aging) can be used to reach the highest HVL value for mammography (considering tube aging and the influence of the paddle).

3.2.3 RRQs for mammography

For detector calibrations at laboratory the easiest approach would be to introduce radiation qualities based on W/Al. For a reference class ionization chamber the difference of calibration coefficients between this and W/Rh is about 0.4 %. At least 3 manufacturers offer mammography systems with Al filtration. A good approach would be to standardize Mo/Mo, W/Al, W/Rh to cover the full range of HVL values and account for other differences in filtration (if reference class mammography chambers are used) by an additional uncertainty of 0.3 %. This is not possible for non-reference class equipment.

Tube voltage [kV]	Mo/30Mo	W/700Al	W/50Rh
25	0.29	0.42	0.47
28	0.32	0.49	0.51
30	0.33	0.53	0.52
35	0.37	0.62	0.56
40	-	0.71	0.60
50	-	0.86	0.70

Table 9: Recommended new radiation qualities (RRQs) for mammography and their respective HVLs. The number in the column headings indicates the filter thickness in μm . The HVLs have been derived by PTB from spectrometry. For W/700Al and W/50Rh, the values were averaged over the results of two different X-ray tubes (MXR 165 and Y.TU 160-D02) with an inherent filtration of 5 mm Be and 0.8 mm Be, respectively.

In addition, for each anode/filter combination it is recommended to introduce a new radiation quality at 50 kV, with an additional Al filter of 0.34 mm thickness, to account for the highest possible HVL value encountered in clinical practice (considering the compression paddle and tube aging).

3.3 Dental X-ray imaging

Devices for intraoral dental X-ray imaging have 1.5 mm Al filters for tube voltages between 50 kV and 70 kV. The most used settings are 60 kV and 70 kV. The corresponding HVL values can be as small as 1.3 mm Al.

An approach could be to extend the range of HVLs to such small values in future standards. But this is not possible within the current overall concept of IEC 61267, because typically all radiation conditions are based on RQR series which is designed in a way that it can be established with any X-ray tube with 2.5 mm Al hardening-equivalent filtration and with anode angles down to 9° . It was concluded that changing RQR radiation qualities should be avoided because they are widely accepted in calibration laboratories, leaving two options for a future update:

1. Introducing dental radiation qualities that are not based on RQR (like the radiation qualities that already exist for mammography)
2. Conclude, that RQR series is good enough for typical calibrations needed for intraoral dental X-ray imaging devices. For such a conclusion, more information on the response of typical detectors is needed.

Further studies are needed to decide on the best way forward.

4 Limitations

The scope of IEC 61267 covers radiation conditions for determining the characteristics of systems or components of medical diagnostic X-ray equipment; this is not limited to dosimeters. The selection of the

recommended radiation qualities (RRQs) from the full range of clinically relevant radiation qualities was made to cover the full range in terms of tube voltages and HVL, allowing the use of these RRQs for any relevant testing. Nevertheless, dosimeters were the only equipment investigated over the RRQs in this project.

Some arguments regarding the selection of RRQs in this document are based on the idea of allowing interpolation with respect to HVL, this is not recommended for XMMs. However, expanding the range of reference radiation qualities will also support the use of XMMs by allowing better coverage of clinically relevant radiation qualities.

The selection of RRQs was verified based on knowledge of the response of two typical ionisation chambers in dependence of energy: one for mammography and one for conventional diagnostics. If other types of ionisation chambers are used, care should be taken, especially if there are differences in wall thickness. However, the improved coverage of clinically relevant radiation qualities should also improve the current situation for testing any systems or components of medical diagnostic X-ray equipment.

5 Dissemination

This document was shared with the IAEA CRP E24024 officers and IEC SC62C WG3 convenor by email (Figure 7). The results are also presented in the annual meeting of IEC WG3 in Goteborg May 2026. The final document will also be shared with them by email after the final approval of MSU.

TraMeXI Deliverable 1: Recommendations on the reference radiation qualities

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 D1_approved-by-consortium_for dissemination.pdf
 823 KB

Dear Zakithi, Olivera and Wes,

Our TraMeXI project is approaching its conclusion, and we have many results to share. While we have already discussed a large part of them, there are a few core deliverables (D) that need to be formally shared with you before they can be submitted to EURAMET for approval.

In this email, I would like to share Deliverable D1, which provides recommendations on the reference radiation qualities that could be included in IEC 61267. The content of D1 will also be presented at our TraMeXI M36 meeting and at the IEC SC62C WG3 annual meeting next week.

Best regards,
 Paula

Figure 7: Dissemination email sent to the IAEA CRP E24024 officers and IEC WG 3 convenor.

6 Literature

- [1] I. Komatina *et al.*, "Calibration services for X-ray multimeters in Europe: current situation and future needs", *Physica Medica*, vol. 136, p. 105055, Aug. 2025, doi: 10.1016/j.ejmp.2025.105055.
- [2] J. Šolc *et al.*, "Photon fluence spectra from various medical X-ray imaging systems measured using a compact cadmium telluride spectrometer", submitted to *JINST*.